

4/17/74

Director of Antiquities
Ministry of Information and Tourism
PO Box 600
Sultanate of Oman
Muscat

Dear Andrew,

Here are the Figures I have on the Marv Dasht sites. These areas are estimated using measurements from the Dorud Zan 1:5,000 map and some 1:20,000 photos. Some sites are not listed either because they are not on either map or photo or were not paced in the field for one reason or another. If any of these missing sites turn out to be of special interest I will try to visit and measure them this summer.

Thanks for the off-prints. Frances also found them of considerable interest since she has now taken up Arabic studies in a very serious way. She spent the winter in London rethinking her life and there is now quite a bit of distance between us which makes me very sad. Anyhow, she is enjoying Arabic thoroughly, will finish her degree this summer, and then no doubt, off to graduate school somewhere. William is taller than I am and is doing fine. Jane has a baby and we seldom see her.

I will be back at Malyan to build a house in late July and for a season from Sept through Nov. Will send you a copy of the latest report when the off-prints arrive. We are definitely in Anshan. Last season a nice collection of late Elamite tablets from a monumental building on the top of site.

Come and visit us at Malyan (or in Columbus for that matter); maybe I will come and visit you on my way home... is there any real down there?

Best wishes,

Sincerely yours,

W.M. Summer

PS- DO YOU HAVE MAP SHOWING LOCATION?
IF NOT, HOW MUCH DETAIL DO YOU WANT?
THAT IS: TO RELOCATE OR JUST TO PERCEIVE
PATTERNS-